

DEVELOPMENT OF COOPERATION BETWEEN HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE LABOR MARKET — AS SOME ASPECTS OF SOLVING SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *The article puts on the agenda the issue of developing cooperation between higher education and the labor market, which examines the labor market and labor relations, the development of professional skills and knowledge, labor protection and standardization, human capital, and lifelong development. training and personnel in the sphere of labor on the basis of modernizing the content of vocational education, attention is focused on improving the personnel training system.*

Keywords: *educational materials, design, professional standards, educational content, methodology, educational technology, network qualification frameworks, educational material scenario, pedagogical science, educational process, computerization of education, integration of science, education and production, credit-modular system, modernization of educational content, security and labor regulation, human capital, labor markets and industrial relations.*

Problem statement:

The current changes in the life of the society pose new problems to the educational system, including the proper organization of the educational process based on the credit-module system, the role and importance of professional standards in the development of normative-legal and organizational-methodical documents of higher education, and state and non-state higher education. problems of development of education and labor market cooperation are becoming urgent.

Under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoev, in COMMITTEE No. 9 of the video selector meeting held in an extended manner on February 5, 2024, special attention is paid to the development of cooperation between higher education and the labor market, "from the 2024/2025 academic year, from the characteristics of professional education professions and specialties, undergraduate education areas and master's specialties on the basis of this, he focused on the issue of introducing the practice of organizing appropriate professional-practical exams, graduation qualification works and defense of master's theses in the employing enterprises and organizations" [4].

Moreover, the transition of modernized Uzbekistan to the path of innovative economic development requires the improvement of the National qualification system in accordance with international norms, which responds quickly to changes in the labor market.

Improving the labor market and labor relations in Uzbekistan, developing professional skills and knowledge, human capital, lifelong learning and modernizing the content of professional education, improving the system of personnel training in the field of labor, for this purpose,

improving the quality and efficiency of education and training competitive personnel, educational technology and its principles issues of drawing up projects of educational materials and applying them in practice are seen as the main task of the day.

Based on this, education is the main factor in the formation of human capital in the education of a new generation that can meet the high demands of the current labor market, the role of professional standards and modern pedagogical technology in the organization of cooperative activities of producers, teachers and students, the role of the national system for evaluating skills and knowledge recognition at the international level, disclosure of the essence of the issues of organization of the educational process under the conditions of the credit-module system is considered the demand of the day.

For effective organization of education, an objective basis for qualitatively quick adaptation to the updated educational process, its credit-module system has emerged, because innovative processes in economic and social life require fundamental changes in education itself. No teacher can be left out of this process sooner or later. The traditional work methods of the teacher remain an objective factor in the birth of the necessity of mastering the qualities of integration of science, education and production or the computerization of teaching.

Literature analysis on the problem: One of the reforms in the education system in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the step-by-step transfer of the educational process to the credit-module system.

In this case, the main focus should be on summarizing the knowledge of students in certain subjects in higher educational institutions, preparing them so that they can compare and compare educational processes and educational programs. In this case, the credit-hours system of education is aimed at independent education and creative assimilation of knowledge based on individuality.

What are the needs and requirements of the credit-module system? That question is something that interests every student. The "credit hour" system was originally developed and developed in the United States. In 1969, the President of Harvard University, Charles Elliott, a famous representative of American education, first introduced the concept of "credit-hour" and in 1870-1880 introduced a system that allowed to measure the amount of science in credit-hours. In 1892, the second stage of introducing the "credit-hour" system began. In this case, the US National Education Committee introduced the concept of "credit" not only for colleges, but also for high schools in order to improve the "college-school" link, standardize curricula in high schools, and later expanded the credit system of evaluating the content of bachelor's programs to the master's and doctoral levels of education.

In 1976, the ministers of education of the European Union countries reached an agreement on the introduction of cooperative study programs between the universities of these countries [7]. But it took more than 10 years to implement this project, develop its financial and legal aspects. Finally, in 1987, during the London Summit of the European Union, the Erasmus (ERASMUS) program was established, which supports student exchange between HEIs of the Union member countries. The purpose of this was to expand the opportunities for students studying in the universities of the EU countries to receive education on mutual exchange for one year or one semester at the universities in the territory of other member states. The European Union allocates a large amount of grants for the support of such international student exchange programs and for the systematic implementation of the program. As a result of the Erasmus program, most of the European universities are starting to open Erasmus offices in order to participate in it.

As a solution to this problem, the Erasmus program in 1989 developed a new credit-module system based on the American credit system and the Dutch higher education system and called it the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS). These regulations included the principles of the educational programs of the universities of the EU countries, the comparison of the subjects offered in them, and the recognition of the subjects studied in foreign universities within the framework of student exchange programs in their own universities. As a result of the introduction of ECTS credit-module system rules, it leads to the development of student exchange between the universities of the EU countries. The educational programs of universities participating in the program begin to gain recognition at the international level [6].

The solve a problem:

The introduction of the credit-module technology of teaching in the higher education institutions of the republic leads to the basis of the world trends in the reform of the national education system. One of the primary tasks of reforms in the education system is the introduction of new teaching and digital technologies to inform education, and in accordance with the requirements of the times, it will be necessary to drastically change the following two components of the educational process: first, teaching technology; and secondly, forms of presentation of educational information using the possibilities of digital technology.

In the multi-level system of higher and post-higher education (bachelor's - master's - doctorate), from general to personal, first of all, a person acquires broad knowledge in a certain direction, and then passes to a narrow specialty through separate educational programs oriented to specialization.

Such a system, from the point of view of the idea and methodology of education, creates an opportunity for the student to develop skills and competencies in interpersonal relations throughout his life. It provides a clear application of knowledge.

The analysis in the study of the introduction of educational credit technology shows that there are specific characteristics in different countries of the world. The feasibility and effectiveness of educational credit technology is seen in the widespread use in the education system of many countries of the world, because the development of educational programs allows students to independently acquire knowledge and increase the level of creative activity in their independent work, which means that the quality of education increases completely.

In this way, the introduction of the technology of educational credit imposes high demands on the composition of contingent personnel, educational-methodical, material-technical support base, and most importantly, the student himself and his attitude to study. Education in credit-module technology increases the demand for independent education of students.

It was concluded that one of the main advantages of academic freedom in institutions of higher education where educational credit technology is introduced: students form their own educational environment with the opportunity to choose professors and teachers. Together with the basic and working curriculum, the students' personal curriculum (SPC – Curriculum) is introduced, which organizes their educational process and defines the educational content.

The task of Gal is to ensure the quality of education in the conditions of the credit education system, for this purpose it is to develop educational and regulatory documents and organizational and methodological norms adapted to International and Professional standards.

Article 34 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" stipulates the development of the State Education Standard of the fields of knowledge, qualification

requirements, curricula and programs of the fields of knowledge with the participation of the Professional standards[1].

Based on the fact that education is the main factor in the formation of human capital as a solution to this priority task, Human capital, Professional standards are becoming the main concept of the day.

The question arises: "Why is there a need to update the normative-legal and organizational-methodical documents of higher education, especially the science programs (syllabi) that form the basis of the educational process"?

It can be observed that some subjects in the curriculum of higher educational institutions (specializations) are not needed in the work process, which causes objections from employers and young graduates. Because, as our president said, our youth are not the youth of yesterday, the renewed Uzbekistan has opened to the world, internationalization and integration issues have come to the fore in education, as in all fields, the higher education institutions where students receive education, the subjects taught in them, the programs used are in line with international standards and the requirements of the labor market, employers needs to be met.

Starting from the 2021/2022 academic year, all state and non-state higher education institutions have switched to the credit-module system of teaching. Educational processes are organized on the basis of educational outcomes, and the educational process, curriculum and programs serve to ensure the achievement of educational outcomes.

Therefore, it is very important to determine universal and professional competencies required by society and the labor market, to achieve results and to constantly update them.

As a solution to these problems, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers dated September 30, 2021 No. 616 "On additional measures to further improve the system of professional qualifications and knowledge"[3] and May 15, 2020 "Professional qualifications, knowledge and skills in the Republic of Uzbekistan On the basis of the national qualifications framework of the Republic of Uzbekistan approved by Resolution No. 287 [2] on measures to organize the activities of the national system of development, state and economic management bodies and employers' associations have developed qualification frameworks for sectors reflecting the specific characteristics of the relevant qualification levels.

It is intended to solve important problems in the implementation of tasks such as the preparation of network qualification frameworks based on the national qualification framework, the development of professional standards, and the updating of professional and higher education standards based on them.

Professional standards are intended to define the job duties of employees, plan their professional development, train specialists, select employees, develop requirements for employment and work activities and organize training, as well as justify the decisions made in the certification of managers and specialists.

Professional standards are an important document (literally a bridge) between the labor market and the education sector, and it is aimed at ensuring that state educational standards, qualification requirements and training programs meet the demands and needs of the labor market, and ensures the quality of professional training of qualified personnel.

Of course, the development of professional standards is a multi-stage and time-consuming process.

The next task was to update state education standards, qualification requirements for educational areas and specialties, curricula, science programs by adapting them to professional standards.

Therefore, "The role of educational and regulatory documents adapted to Professional Standards and International Standards is incomparable in ensuring the quality of education.

The following important criteria are taken into account when developing professional standards:

- trends of socio-economic development of the state in the medium and long term;
- labor market requirements;
- advanced technologies, types of raw materials and modern equipment used in production, as well as in the provision of services.

Professional standards are used by employers in the following cases:

- determining the functional obligations of employees in order to draw up employment contracts and job descriptions;

- description of job requirements and ensuring the quality of their performance;

- elimination of duplication of duties;

- classification of professional activities and assignment of qualification categories to employees;

- development of a labor remuneration system taking into account the specific features of production, labor and management organization;

- organization of training in order to improve the professional skills of employees;

- development of internal procedures, including staff tables;

- development of incentive system and determination of types and amounts of incentive payments;

- management of personnel policy.

The development of professional standards is a multi-stage and time-consuming process, which requires not only an enterprising developer, but also the organization of an effective working group of developers. Among them should be an organization willing to coordinate the development of professional standards and undertake to ensure compliance with reasonable requirements.

As the next task, it is necessary to work on updating the state educational standards, qualification requirements for educational areas and specialties, curricula, and science programs by adapting them to professional standards. In this regard, the analysis shows that there are many problems.

We know that the primary basis of the continuous education system and the place of activity of pedagogues, training, that is, the lesson, is the most necessary issue. At the moment, in all educational institutions, training is conducted in the manner left by our forefathers, but in reality based on the level of professional training and personal education of the pedagogue.

There is no sufficient basis for the statements that we are providing students with knowledge using modern pedagogical technology. Today, in our country, the extent to which professors and teachers use pedagogical technology in the teaching process is controversial. Our research shows this. Such an unconscious state can destroy all efforts made in the field of education. It would not be an exaggeration to say that the education sector is in one place.

Every pedagogue should keep the attention of the students in the audience until the end of the training session, turn the knowledge shown in the science program (syllabus) and the national qualities that must be instilled into the spirit of the young generation into his way of life. At the same time, in order to convey this knowledge and qualities to young people, it is necessary to organize an educational session, following 6 principles and more than 30 rules of didactics, using a number of traditional, non-traditional and more than 200 interactive methods, existing information and communication technology and didactic materials. Even the most talented pedagogue cannot fulfill this task. To the question of how to do something that cannot be done, we answer that it is possible. One of the most important aspects of this process is the adaptation of education organization to world standards, that is, the transition of education to the "Credit-module" system and the development of the "Profession and position standards" that are its basis, and the State education standard, qualification requirements and curriculum (syllabus) are added to it. adaptation, as the main way of their implementation, world pedagogues, who conducted research on this problem, found a way and called it "educational technology, design of educational materials based on its principles".

Conclusion:

Based on the above, the following suggestions and recommendations can be made. In particular:

In order to solve and coordinate problems in the field of education and make proposals, a seminar-meeting should be held twice a year in cooperation with the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan, ensuring the participation of all representatives of the field of education in the Republic.

Not to ignore the proposals of social organizations aimed at the development of strategies and tactics and coordination of resources for the normal functioning of the educational system.

Introducing the concept of "Education throughout life" into the republican education system, according to which a person (that is, an elderly, mentally disabled, unemployed or other type of person who could not get education on time) has the right to education throughout his life. This model of education is the development of a targeted and continuous professional education state program.

One of the urgent problems of the education sector is the need for production enterprises, state and non-state sector employers, and it is necessary to establish a continuous monitoring.

Today's global problem in the activity of higher education institutions envisages the creation of factors for establishing a high level of connection between the education sector and personnel consumers. For this, adaptation of educational and teaching-methodical documents to professional standards is considered as the most urgent issue of the day.

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